

What happens inside a moist chamber culture?

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Abstract: An entire subset of moist chamber cultures was used to document both the internal temperature and the moistness of the filter paper surface. These metrics are presented and studied in the context of both the temperature and the humidity of the room where the experiment was conducted. Overall, it seems that internal and external temperatures are independent, but internal and external measurements of air humidity and surface moistness seem to be related. The data presented herein are meant to generate only a discussion, but should be supported more robustly by experiments dedicated to studying the limitations of the moist chamber technique culture in the future.

Keywords: culturing, microbiology, monitoring, myxomycetes, Petri dish.

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In the modern context of myxomycete research it is very common to see an investigator using the moist chamber technique as it applies to myxomycetes for recording data in a laboratory environment. As mentioned by several authors, this technique has been very useful during the process of global documentation of these organisms, at least based on sporocarp data (Alexopoulos 1953, Stephenson and Stempen 1994). In recent years, the technique has been mentioned to be one of the key methods to study myxomycetes due to its complementary character to both field-based and molecular-driven approaches (Wrigley de Basanta and Estrada Torres, 2022).

During 2015-2016, in an effort to document myxomycetes along a gradient of precipitation in the dryer parts of Costa Rica (Arenas-Taborda et al. 2021), we established 720 moist chamber cultures. From those, we selected randomly, a total of 97 cultures (about 13% of total effort) for keeping track of both the internal temperature and surface moistness for 10 weeks, the length of time for which we decided to study the entire set of moist chambers. We also determined the barometric pressure, the temperature, and the humidity of the room where the moist chambers were set up. The goal of this little observational experiment was to increase our understanding of the dynamics taking place inside the moist chamber cultures during a real run intended to generate scientific data on these organisms.

We used infrared thermometers and pin-based protimeter moisture meters to obtain data on the internal temperature and moistness of the moist chambers. For this task, every week, right before checking the cultures for myxomycetes, we would place the moist chamber in a measuring station and open the lid

about half an inch. This aperture was just enough to insert the moistness probe and to obtain the temperature reading of the filter paper, all within 10 seconds or so. Additionally, to determine some characteristics of the laboratory where the experiment was taking place, both a barometer and a temperature/relative humidity meter were placed next to the stacks of Petri dishes. For quantification, both room and culture temperature were recorded in the Celsius scale ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), culture moistness was reported as surface moisture content (% w/w), relative humidity was recorded in the room air (%), and atmospheric pressure was measured in hectoPascals (hPa). From the 97 cultures studied in that manner, 33 were set up with material from a wet non-seasonal premontane forest, 37 used materials from a moist seasonal premontane forest, and 27 were set up with substrates from a lowland seasonal dry forest in Costa Rica.

The average recorded temperature, barometric pressure and relative humidity values of the room were determined as $23.1\pm 1.9^{\circ}\text{C}$, 880.4 ± 1.5 hPa and $73.7\pm 5.6\%$ during the 10-week experiment. Inside the moist chambers, the average temperature and surface moistness were $20.5\pm 1.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $31.3\pm 8.4\%$ w/w, respectively (see weekly values in Table 1). The observed variation in room temperature between the lowest and highest recorded weekly values was 7.7 degrees, whereas the same difference for culture values was 5.2 degrees, with a subsequent difference of 32.0% lower temperature inside the moist chambers. Contrastingly, the observed variation in room humidity between highest and lowest values was 23.1%, whereas the same variation in culture moistness was 35.0%, indicating that the variation inside the moist chambers was 34.0% higher than the variation of a similar metric in the laboratory. Despite this observation, it is important to remember that the two measurements are different, and it would be interesting to carry out the comparison with the same metric.

The average moistness value inside the moist chamber during the entire period represented about 63% of the highest possible value of 50% w/w and the decreasing values between weeks 2 and 5 and between weeks 7 and 10 displayed a loss rate of 3% per week. During the experiment, water was added to the moist chambers during week 1, at the start of the experiment, and during week 5, after reading the values. These results indicated that given the room conditions where the experiment was carried out, internal moistness decreased slow but steadily until more water was added, as expected. However, such surface moistness loss rate seemed less accelerated than in temperate areas, where the air humidity is invariably lower.

Table 1. Ranges of room humidity (RH) and room temperate (RT) as well as culture temperature (T) and culture moistness (W) all 97 studied cultures during the 10-week period.

Week	Range of RH (%)	Range of RT ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Average T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Average W (% w/w)
W1	66.6-80.1	22.2-26.4		
W2	57.1-84.3	19.9-28.6	20.7 ± 1.2	32.6 ± 8.7
W3	54.9-76.6	20.1-28.5	20.4 ± 0.8	31.2 ± 8.9
W4	53.0-81.6	20.3-27.8	20.4 ± 1.0	30.1 ± 8.3
W5	55.9-81.3	20.2-29.1	20.4 ± 1.0	29.5 ± 8.0
W6	60.0-82.6	20.0-28.3	20.5 ± 0.5	30.5 ± 8.5
W7	62.5-83.1	19.9-28.0	20.9 ± 0.9	33.9 ± 7.8
W8	55.4-80.9	19.8-28.0	19.5 ± 1.1	32.3 ± 8.2
W9	62.1-83.5	19.8-27.0	21.3 ± 1.1	31.5 ± 8.7
W10	55.6-79.2	19.5-27.6	20.1 ± 1.6	30.3 ± 7.7

The internal temperature of the moist chamber cultures was clearly very steady, except during weeks 8 and 9, which coincided with the two lowest values overall. However, no direct mathematical relationship between this variable and room temperature was observed (Fig. 1), and instead, the highest correlation values of the culture average temperature were observed with both the minimum and maximum room humidity instead ($\rho=0.82$ and 0.86 , respectively). Contrastingly, the average moistness inside the moist chamber varied in a very similar manner to the humidity of the room displaying high values during weeks 2 and 7 and low values during weeks 5 and 10 (Fig. 2). In this case, the association between the two variables showed a moderate correlation value ($\rho=0.67$).

Figure 1. Average values of both room temperature (RT) and culture temperature (T) for the ten weeks of the experiment described herein.

Figure 2. Average values of both room humidity (RH) and culture moistness (W) for the ten weeks of the experiment described herein.

These observations seem to point out that in the experiment that provided the results for the Arenas-Taborda experiment, the moist chamber cultures were affected more directly by the room humidity than

by the room temperature. Such remark makes sense when it is considered that some differences in microenvironmental conditions are simply determined by the position of the culture in space dedicated for examination. For instance, cultures are commonly stacked in columns that can range between 5-15 Petri dishes in most experiments (Fig. 3), and it would make sense that the cultures in the upper part of the stack display different microenvironments that those at the bottom. For this reason, some people recommend a rotation of cultures every week by placing the top cultures in bottom positions of a new stack and vice versa. However, this procedure would only affect those cultures in the end positions of stacks (the ones that really are switching) because the cultures in the middle of the stack would always be in the middle.

Figure 3. Stacks of moist chamber cultures documented herein. As observed, each culture has a specific microclimate given by the three-dimensional characteristics of the setup.

In a similar manner, if several stacks of cultures are placed next to each other forming a group, the dimensions of the entire setup (e.g., how many cultures wide by how many cultures deep) would determine some of the microclimatic characteristics as well. For this reason, in addition to the culture rotation within a stack, a stack rotation within a group could also be advisable. It would be interesting to carry out an entire experiment measuring those microclimatic variables again, but also considering the observations just mentioned herein.

From the 720 moist chambers studied by Arenas-Taborda et al. (2021), only 174 cultures or 24% yielded any positive evidence of myxomycetes. This is a very low value when compared to many other studies, but I have the impression that tropical substrates in tropical laboratories are more difficult for yielding myxomycete sporocarps than similar substrates in temperate laboratories, which can possibly point out at some differences in air quality (e.g., temperature and humidity) between regions. It would be interesting to carry out an experiment to test this idea. Interestingly, the cultures made with material from the wet non-seasonal premontane forest displayed a slightly higher positive percentage (28%) than the average, whereas those from the moist seasonal premontane forest and the lowland seasonal dry forest generated lower values (21 and 22%, respectively).

Contrastingly, the 33 cultures from the wet non-seasonal premontane forest yielded six morphospecies of myxomycetes, the 37 moist chambers from the moist seasonal premontane forest

produced only three morphospecies, and the 27 cultures from the lowland seasonal dry forest yielded nine morphospecies. These results would clearly indicate what many researchers have pointed out in recent years with respect to dry ecosystems being productive localities for studying myxomycetes. This observation seems to be a pattern in both tropical and temperate areas as well. A recent study from Stephenson et al. (2025) in the western section of the continental United States showed the presence of 419 morphospecies of myxomycetes, about 91% of the 460 morphospecies documented in the moister eastern section, with only 35% of the total collecting effort.

A lot of biodiversity or ecological work on myxomycetes has been done using the moist chamber technique, but little effort has been dedicated to understanding the limitations of the technique for those purposes. Since one of the research pressures today, at least in developing countries, is to come up with applications using biodiversity data, I feel that we should study the technique a little more so we can understand it better and standardize a protocol that can let us make comparisons more accurately. If we get to that point, maybe we can come up with real applications for the data represented in the sporocarps that we see in those cultures. For now, at least based on what was presented herein, it seems that what happens inside a moist chamber culture resembles partially what happens in the room where the experiment is being carried out.

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